

Effect of Immersion Program on the Cookery Skills of Grade Nine Students

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Abstract. This study investigated the impact of an immersion program on the cookery skills of grade nine students at Sta. Cruz National High School. Utilizing a quasi-experimental design with non-equivalent control and experimental groups, the research involved 50 students from two sections: 25 in the control group (section A-Mabini) and 25 in the experimental group (section B-Aquino). Both groups were heterogeneous, ensuring a comparable performance range among participants. The study employed a face-to-face instructional modality, with pre- and post-tests administered using a 25-item rubric-based assessment to measure the students' cookery skills. The pretest evaluated the baseline skills, while the post-test assessed the impact of the immersion program. Data analysis aimed to determine significant differences in performance between the groups and the overall effectiveness of the immersion program in enhancing students' cookery skills. The findings are intended to inform educational strategies and policy recommendations for improving practical skill development in home economics.

KEY WORDS

1. Immersion 2. cookery skills 3. Quasi-experimental design intervention

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1. Introduction

Cookery is an area in Home Economics that deals with the practice or skill of preparing and cooking foods. In this subject, students are being taught the importance of food nutrients, ethical food issues, safe food storage, preparation, and handling of foods. This also includes budgeting, food preservation, and cooking business. A student who will be well-motivated by the teacher may have a good foundation for cookery in the future, students may be involved in Food and Nutrition Management, or as Dietitian's in hospitals or companies, and maybe a Nutritionist (Rupp, 2019). Different benefits can be taken from Cookery. Many believe that Home Economics has an extremely important place not only at home and in business, but more so in the educational system. Home Economics is an old subject in the past curriculum; at present, it is still a helpful subject that will help students in their future endeavors. Through this subject, the students gain self-confidence and preparedness which are helpful attributes that they will need inside and outside their classroom (Wrangham, 2019). Cookery students will acquire skills that may help in taking care of their household and may have the potential of a more productive field outside of the home. Through Cookery lessons, physical fitness is connected, since it deals with foods, therefore the well-being of the body is considered. Body

fitness may be achieved through proper food and nutrition. Teachers must always remind H.E. students that like any other areas of H.E. Cookery will bring benefits to them; let us remember that Cooking is a healthy way to nourish your body, mind, and spirit (Wayt, 2019). Learning cooking skills can help you prepare food effectively and enhance the quality of your meals. Chefs can develop these skills by studying different techniques and types of cuisine. By reviewing some fundamental capabilities, you can select options that best suit your needs. In this article, we provide 25 examples of key cooking abilities, list steps for how to improve them, and explain how to list them in a resume (Organ, 2019). Cooking skills are abilities that allow you to cook safely and effectively in your workplace. Although some cooking skills are specific culinary techniques that help you make better-tasting food, there are also professional skills for cooks that allow you to perform work in ways that appeal to customers and impress employers. Typically, the focus on workplace cooking skills is on whether you can prepare food safely for a target customer base (Pringle, 2020). Cleanliness is an important skill for cooking because it encourages food and kitchen safety, which benefits customers and your team by helping you create a pleasant and healthy environment. As a cook, you can show your cleanliness by cleaning messes in your workplace kitchen and sanitizing tools and dishes with the proper methods. Improve this skill by taking classes on food safety, cleanliness, and sanitation either online or at local workshops (Wrangham Conklin-Brittain, 2020). Along with food and kitchen hygiene, ensuring proper food safety is paramount in a cooking position. You ensure that food is safe to eat, often following industry standards or local health regulations to prevent food-borne illnesses. For example, knowing what temperature to keep and cooking foods safely can prevent spoiling or illness. You also usually uphold health codes,

like keeping raw and cooked foods separate (Pollard, 2019). When you're skilled in teamwork, you can work more effectively with other cooks and employees in your workplace, like servers. You might use teamwork in various situations at work, including when you cook in a kitchen with others, when you rotate cleaning duties with your team members, and when you receive food orders from servers in the dining area. To get better at working with a team, practice your communication skills and think about how you can contribute to a positive work environment with your words and actions (Luke, 2021). Kitchen management is a helpful skill to develop for any position in food service, and sometimes being a kitchen manager is a specific role itself. Learning tasks like ordering food and supplies, creating menus, or updating staff schedules can help you hone management skills for a restaurant, for example. Kitchen management skills also often incorporate other ones, like food safety, communication, leadership, and team building (Smith, 2020). In the Division of Davao Del Sur, particularly in Sta. Cruz National High School, teachers must look for programs to make learning happen for the learners. The researcher as a TLE teacher exhausts her effort in looking for a program to enhance the cookery skills of the students. Hence, this study of developing an immersion program in developing the skills of cookery students.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

*1.1.1. Cooking Skills—*Cooking skills are crucial in preventing and reducing chronic diet-related diseases and obesity. These skills, targeting all age groups, are linked to improved diet quality and better health outcomes. However, the optimal age for learning these skills remains unknown (Zohar et al., 2022). A UK survey highlighted that learning to cook is considered an essential life skill, ranking fifth among modern living skills (Akram, 2019). Cooking interventions vary in teaching methods, including information provision, demonstrations, and hands-

on sessions, and target children, teenagers, and adults (Beal, 2020). Early acquisition of cooking skills might positively impact dietary habits later in life, similar to other skills like math and reading (Nunn Qian, 2020). Introducing cooking lessons in schools can help students lead independent lives and develop the habit of preparing their meals, promoting responsibility and healthier eating habits (Caravita, 2019; Gellert, 2021; Öste, 2020). Moreover, learning to cook in school can shift students' focus from processed foods to home-cooked meals, potentially sparking interest in culinary careers (Gilbert, 2019; Guichard, 2020).

1.1.2. Cookery—Cookery, a branch of Home Economics, teaches students about food nutrients, ethical food issues, safe food storage, and preparation. It also covers budgeting, food preservation, and cooking business, providing a foundation for future careers in nutrition and dietetics (Stone, 2021). Cookery lessons enhance self-confidence and preparedness, essential for personal and professional success (Velez, 2020). Physical fitness is connected to cookery as it involves proper nutrition, promoting overall well-being (Braver, 2019). Involving parents and community groups can enhance cooking classes, making them more effective (Cookston, 2021). Hands-on activities in cooking classes, such as drawing ingredients or writing journals, keep students engaged and reinforce learning (Noah, 2019; Wilson, 2019). Sharing personal stories and the origins of recipes can make cooking more relatable and exciting for students (Murray, 2020).

1.1.3. Journaling and Hands-on Activities—Hands-on activities in cooking classes, like drawing ingredients and journaling, help students stay engaged and reinforce their learning. Journaling before and after cooking classes allows students to reflect on their experiences and deepen their understanding of recipes and cooking processes (Jin, 2021). Connecting cooking activities to personal stories and local

food sources can enhance students' interest and willingness to try new recipes (Murray, 2020).

Integrating cooking lessons into school curricula is essential for fostering independent living skills, promoting healthier eating habits, and potentially inspiring culinary careers. Hands-on activities and journaling can enhance the effectiveness of these lessons, making cooking an engaging and educational experience for students.

1.2. Synthesis—The articles above emphasized the negative and positive effects of immersion programs on the cookery skills of grade 9 learners. Noting the results of the studies conducted by the previous researchers, they have determined the effectiveness and shortcomings of the immersion programs. The following is the sum-up of the causes of the positive impact of immersion programs on students who experienced the new normal education. First, it fulfills the diversified needs of learning of students of all levels. Second, students learn at their own pace. Lastly, immersion promoted positive effects on skills acquisition. However, some studies have shown the negative impact of immersion programs which resulted in the decreased rate of academic performance of students. Parents had claimed that time allotment to finish the learning tasks, and too many activities incorporated in the immersion have burdened the learners academically.

1.3. Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on the proposition of Arora (2016) who said that cookery is both an art and technology. Food preparation is a modern term in professional cookery. It denotes preparation and cooking. It follows a flow pattern that commences with the purchasing and selection of materials, their handling, processing, and the ultimate presentation of dishes to customers, where "food service" takes over. In French, the word *cuisine* denotes –the art of cooking- preparing dishes and the place kitchen in which they are prepared. This is supported

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study.

by Lebowitz (2018) who expressed that cooking skills are a vital need for healthy and happy survival. Everyone should know why learning to cook is important and the benefits of learning cooking skills. There are many interesting aspects associated with the importance of learning cooking skills. Cooking skills are necessary to learn as they help you wherever you are. If you

are working all day and feeling exhausted and know how to cook, you can alleviate yourself. You might want to engage yourself to divert your mind, so cooking skills are the best in this regard. The importance of learning cooking skills is incredible, and you can easily realize why cooking is important by acknowledging the benefits of learning cooking skills.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—This study seeks to determine the effect of the Immersion Program on the cookery skills of grade nine students. Eventually, it also seeks to determine the

magnitude of the effect of the action initiated by the researcher on the cookery skills of the research subjects. Moreover, it seeks answers to the following sub-problems:

- (1) What are the pretest scores of the grade nine learners in both controlled and experimental groups?
- (2) What are the post-test scores of the grade nine learners in both the controlled and experimental groups?
- (3) Is there a significant difference between the post-scores of the controlled and experimental groups?
- (4) What is the magnitude effect of the immersion program on the cookery skills skills of grade nine learners?

1.5. Null Hypothesis—The null hypothesis in this study will be tested at a 0.05 level of significance. H01. There is no significant difference between the post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups. H02. The immersion program does not affect the cooking skills of grade nine learners.

study, particularly in policy redirection recommending an immersion program to implement in developing cookery skills, particularly for the Grade 9 students. The department’s key officials oversee developing the policy analysis that will be implemented in the field schools. The Regional Office will closely monitor this policy. The Central office will receive feedback for reorientation of the implemented policy. The study also acknowledges school administrators as recipients of its findings. Local policies and

1.6. Significance of the Study—The following are considered beneficiaries of this action research. DEPED. DepEd Officials will benefit from the results and findings of this

initiatives can be formulated and implemented within the immersion program to effectively address the educational requirements of students, with a specific focus on cookery skills. Teachers. The primary beneficiaries of this study are the teachers, who serve as the front-line educators and have direct interaction with the learners. The teacher may seek to ascertain the strategy that will be employed in the immersion program to cultivate an enjoyable and meaningful experience during immersion. Future Researchers. A study about the effect of immersion programs on cookery skills in Junior High School is hereby recommended as another study for future researchers.

1.7. Definition of Terms—To make this study comprehensive, the following terms are

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, the data gathering procedure, and the data analysis. We will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi-experimental research design, which was a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design was a good design when the researcher had ac-

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz National High School, Sta. Cruz South District. The subjects of this study were the 50 grade nine students – 25 were from section A-Mabini which comprised the controlled group and 25 were from section B-Aquino composed the experimental

operationally and conceptually defined. Immersion Program refers to the method used by the researcher in teaching cookery where she developed an immersion program beyond classroom-based instruction. She used this program in teaching cookery, particularly in enhancing cookery skills. An immersion program refers to a hands-on and experiential learning approach where students are placed in real-world workplace settings related to their chosen technical or vocational field (Aggarwal, 2019). Cookery Skills refers to the ability of the grade nine learners to demonstrate the common and core competencies of cookery through hands-on activities.

cess to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study were an intact group of learners. This design was represented as follows:

group. The composition of these two sections was heterogeneous therefore learners of sections A and B had identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

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01	X	02
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- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the controlled group
- 04 Posttest of the controlled group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	No. of Learners
1 Section A	25
2 Section B	25
Total	50

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the face-to-face modality during classroom instruction. The pre- and post-performance test equivalent to 25 test items was administered using rubrics. The pretest was administered to all subjects before the treatment.

The pretest was very helpful in assessing the cooking skills of the learners. On the other hand, a post-test was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the cooking skills of grade nine learners, the following continuum was used based on the DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of the data-gathering procedure, the researcher drafted letters and sought permission for the research study conducted and were sent to Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO VI, Schools Division Superintendent, Division of Davao Del Sur, and Mrs. Josephine Aragon, School principal of Sta. Cruz National High School. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and had it validated by the experts, preferably the experts of the study. After permission had been granted this study was conducted in Sta. Cruz National High School after the research questionnaire had been thor-

oughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher administered a pretest to both the controlled and experimental classes and eventually commenced her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered a posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the cookery skills of the subjects from controlled and experimental groups in the pretest and post-test. Eta square was used

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge, skills, and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

to measure the magnitude of the effect of the Immersion Program on the cookery skills of the grade nine learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented a discussion of the problems in this study. These were discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners, and the Significant Relationship between the pre-tests and post-test scores.

3.1. Pre-Test Score of Learners—Table 1 were the pre-test scores of the grade nine students. The controlled group got a mean of 38.65 or Developing while the experimental group got a mean of 38.80 or Developing. This meant that students at this level possessed the minimum knowledge, skills, and core understandings but needed help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.

It was gleaned from the table that during the pre-test the, rating of the experimental group was slightly higher over the control group, although both belong to the Developing level, and we could consider that the lead was not significant. This finding was congruent to the idea of Archer (2015) who said that teachers should select only the criterion types that were appropriate for the targeted standards or outcomes, as well as the specific qualities for which they

Table 1: Pre-Test Scores of Learners

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	25	38.65	77.30	Developing
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	25	38.80	77.60	Developing

wanted to provide feedback to learners. Having said this, I wanted to make a case study for the value of immersion programs including the Impact Criteria on student’s skills and performance in cookery. The more tasks were set in an authentic context, the more important it was to consider the overall impact of the resulting performance. Indeed, we wanted to the students to move beyond “compliance” thinking to consider the overall effectiveness of their work given the intended purpose and target audience. This was supported by Butera (2015) who said that learning takes place in student’s heads where it is invisible to others. This meant that learning was assessed through performance: what students can do with their learning. Assessing students’ performance involved assessments that were formal or informal, high – or

low-stakes, anonymous or public, individual, or collective.

3.1.1. Post-Test Score of Learners—As shown in Table 2 were the post-test scores of the grade nine learners. The control group got a mean of 33.79 or Approaching while the experimental group gained a mean of 44.25 or Approaching. It was gleaned from the table that during the post-test the experimental group had a higher mean rating than the control group. It got a mean rating increase of 12.92 from a mean rating of 30.40 to 44.25. This meant that students in the controlled group at this level had developed the fundamental knowledge skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, could transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.

Table 2: Post-Test Scores of Learners

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Post-test	25	43.75	87.50	Approaching Proficiency
Experimental Group				
Post-test	25	45.30	90.60	Proficient

On the other hand, students in the experimental group at this level had developed the fundamental knowledge skills and core understandings and could transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.

This finding was congruent with the idea of Gellert (2021) who said that When students and

kids were taught at an early age in school how to cook, they developed the habit of preparing their food even when they were at home. This was because they tended to take more responsibility for the food they were cooking, which matters very much to them. Since they had prepared their meals, they were curious to taste what

they cooked, thus consuming the food (Gellert, 2021). When taught in schools about the procedures and the different methods of preparing food, the learners gave it a more serious approach like the ones they gave to other subjects like math. This prompted them to shift their skills and took them home, where they were practiced further. Regular home practice on the skills learned at school produced good cooks which wouldn't be so if they learned how to cook while at home (Öste, 2020).

3.3. Test on the Significant Difference be-

tween the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score - Shown in Table 3 were the tests on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.10 with a p-value of .0351 which was less than the .05 level of significance which means that there was a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post-test scores of the grade nine students. This implied that the application of the immersion approach as a strategy had developed the cookery skills of the grade nine students.

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	38	-5.10	.0351	Significant

This finding was in line with the statement of Gilbert (2019) who disclosed that students or kids who were used to processed ready-made food had a problem with their eating habits. When the schools taught how to cook, the concept of food to them changed, and instead of perceiving it as a finished good, the students saw every ingredient that was used to prepare a meal. As they got used to preparing their various types of food and eating them, they shifted their focus from processed foods which they had no guarantee of their preparation and began to embrace cooked food. When schools offered cooking lessons and students began to embrace the art of cooking, this might trigger an interest in some students to take cooking as a career. This gave them the chance to perfect their basic skills and offered a platform for creativity in

the kitchen. The skills learned in school had a great benefit when one decided to open a diner or seek employment as a chef (Guichard, 2020).

3.4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference

between the Pretest and Post-test Scores of the Grade Nine Students - Table 4 highlighted the test of immersion approach on the cookery skills of grade nine students. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.291 which signified a large effect. This implied that the use of the immersion approach in teaching was effective in developing the cookery skills of grade nine students. It also implied that students learn when they perform rather than watching the teacher doing the activity. This finding was anchored on the principle of learning by doing and the principle of immersion.

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post-test Scores of the Grade Nine Students

N	t-value	Eta ²	Descriptive Value	Decision
50	-4.10	0.291	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

This finding was in line with the idea of Wrangham (2019) who expressed that different benefits taken from Cookery. Many believed that Home Economics had an extremely important place not only at home and in business, but more so in the educational system. Home Economics was an old subject in the past curriculum; at present, it is still a helpful subject that will help students in their future endeavors. Through this subject, the students gain self-confidence and preparedness which are helpful attributes that they need inside and outside their classroom (Wrangham, 2019). Cookery students acquired skills that may help in taking care of their household and had the potential for a more productive life outside of the home. Employing Cookery lessons, physical fitness was connected, since it deals with food, therefore the well-being of the body was considered. Body fitness may achieve through proper food and nutrition. Teachers must always remind H.E. students that like any other area of H.E., Cookery brings benefits to them; let us remember that Cooking is a healthy way to nourish your body, mind, and spirit (Wayt, 2019).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displayed the summary of the findings, conclusions, and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of the immersion program on the cookery skills of grade nine students. This study made use of a quasi-experimental research design, which was a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design was a good design when the researcher had access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study were an intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz National High School, Sta. Cruz South District. The subjects of this study were 50 grade nine students – 25 were from section A which comprised the control group and 25 were from section B which was the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was heterogeneous therefore learners of sections A and B had identical range of performance. This study was made of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the application of the performance approach had developed the immersion skills of grade nine students. It also revealed that there was a magnitude of difference between the post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn. The pre-test scores of the grade nine learners in both the controlled and experimental groups at the Developing level. The post-test scores of the control group were at the Approaching Proficiency level while the post-test scores of the experimental group were at the Proficient level.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered. It is recommended that teachers across subject areas and grade levels apply an immersion approach to achieve optimum learning. Learners learn best if they immerse themselves in the activity rather than just as onlookers to the teacher demonstrating. The school heads should promote the application of the immersion approach by institutionalizing its application through a memorandum that the said approach should be used in classroom instruction,

particularly in the teaching of cookery and to be observed by the school head during clinical supervision. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the application of the immersion approach be conducted exploring another dimension in the curriculum that will emerge as an academic problem to be resolved.

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